

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ARTS IN NURSING

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**PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND ITS IMPACT ON
PROFESSIONAL VALUES OF STAFF NURSES IN A TERTIARY GOVERNMENT
HOSPITAL IN PAMPANGA**

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14 May 2025

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Acceptance Page

This Thesis/Dissertation of **VINA L. SALANGSANG** titled: "**PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AND ITS IMPACT ON PROFESSIONAL VALUES OF STAFF NURSES IN A TERTIARY GOVERNMENT HOSPITAL IN PAMPANGA**" is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree **Master in Arts of Nursing**.

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Biographical Sketch

Vina L. Salangang is a dedicated and proficient nurse leader with over 15 years of significant experience in clinical and administrative nursing roles, both in the Philippines and abroad. She is presently the Chief Nurse at the OFW Hospital in San Fernando, Pampanga, where she oversees the planning, organization, and management of the entire Nursing Service Department to ensure quality patient care is delivered. Her professional journey started when she passed the Nurse Licensure Examination in 2009. Since that time, she has assumed multiple nursing positions at respected facilities like St. John Paul II Medical Center, AC Sacred Heart Medical Center, and Mother Teresa of Calcutta Medical Center, where she gained extensive experience in general nursing, neonatal intensive care, pediatric intensive care, and administrative leadership. Her international experience includes working as a staff nurse at the Security Forces Hospital Program and the Prince Sultan Cardiac Center in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, where she honed her abilities in outpatient and pediatric post-op cardiac care, respectively.

She has consistently and actively engaged in various initiatives for quality improvement, such as taking part in the internationally recognized Magnet Accreditation Program and the Quality and Safety Councils during her tenure Security Forces Hospital Program. Her experience in leadership and understanding of the evolving demands in healthcare motivated her to investigate the subject: "Perceived Organizational Support and Its Impact on Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Tertiary Government Hospital in Pampanga". The findings of her research provided insightful viewpoints on the connection between organizational support and the professional values maintained by nursing professionals.

Acknowledgement

The journey to completing this thesis was a challenging process. I am fortunate that I have a great support system that helped me be prepared for every situation. This thesis holds a great personal significance for me as I embraced a greater responsibility in my professional career – the study on organizational support and professional values is not only timely but very relevant to my current experiences.

First, I want to thank the Almighty God, for without His kindness, this would have not been completed.

Second, to my family, especially to my husband – Angelo and my children – Adi and Aziel, your love served as my foundation. I am also thankful to my mother and to my sister – Nova, for their support and faith in me.

Third, my sincerest gratitude to Asst. Professor Queenie R. Ridulme, my thesis adviser, whose advise, and unwavering support helped me make this research into what it is today.

Fourth, I would also like to express my gratitude to Asst. Professor Irma I. Almoneda and the esteemed panel members – Dr. Rita C. Ramos, Ms. Maria Rita V. Tamse and Ms. Grace Riego De Dios, whose valuable inputs improved the quality of this study.

Fifth, I would especially want to thank Ms. Madonna Valenzuela, who made sure the dependability and accuracy of my conclusions.

Finally, my sincerest gratitude to my colleagues and friends at the OFW Hospital, for their unwavering support and encouragement.

To the road ahead, In Omnia Paratus! – Ready for anything!

Dedication

This research is sincerely dedicated to the compassionate and resilient nurses who tirelessly care for the well-being of others. Your commitment to caring for and advocating for patients continuously inspires the drive to enhance the knowledge and practice of the nursing profession.

To my family and friends, mentors and colleagues, whose support and encouragement have been my pillar of strength throughout this journey—your belief in me has been my motivation.

Abstract

Nurses are the backbone of healthcare. They play a critical role in the delivery of healthcare services, especially in high demand settings like the tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. Designated as a multi-specialty end-referral hospital in Region 3, staff nurses in this hospital are faced with issues related to understaffing, overcrowding and limited institutional resources.

Given the current scarcity of literature exploring the impact of perceived organizational support to nurses' professional values, this study aimed to examine the relationship between organizational support and professional values, identifying domains that mostly influence organizational support and offering insights to enhance workplace practices for nurses. This study utilized correlational research design which involved 172 staff nurses assigned on various nursing units in the tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. Following the approval of the Research Ethics Committee, the data collection was made through a two-part online survey. Mean, standard deviation and Spearman rho correlation coefficient were used in the data analyses.

The results of this study showed that the level of perceived organizational support of nurses was high, as well as the level of professional values. Particularly, the values under the domain activism had the strongest correlation to the nurses' perceived organizational support.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Professional Values, staff nurses, Tertiary Government Hospital, Pampanga

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Chapter I

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Nurses comprise of about 40% to 50% of the total workforce in nearly all health care settings. This group of professionals provide non-stop patient care regardless of holidays and disasters (Hospital Nursing Service Administration Manual, 2019). Given their vital role, the organizations should find ways on how to support and prioritize their staff welfare (Moloney, Fieldes & Jacobs, 2020). This support is not only crucial for retention and morale but also because professional behavior in the workplace may be impacted by this kind of support. In relation to this, when a group of professionals like nurses adjust their behaviors at work, they use professional values as their guidelines (Poorchangizi, et al., 2017). Weis and Schank (as cited by Poreddi, et al., 2021) asserted that values in a profession are the basis for conducts that are established by professional bodies and are employed to assess the reliability of a person or institution. Specifically in the nursing context, these are the principles that nurses follow in order to do their work ethically and with quality (Habeeb, 2022). The decision-making and professional growth of nurses is rooted from their values.

Moreover, it is important that employees feel valued and supported as it adds motivation for them to work well (Shanock, 2019). This connection between support and performance is evident in the study of Kumar & Ansari (2020), where there was a substantial connection between the perceived organizational support (POS) and work performance of women faculty members in universities. According to Eisenberger et al. (2020), perceived organizational support (POS) pertains to an individual's beliefs that the institution values his/her hard work and minds about his/her wellbeing. Thus,

in the case of nurses, the organizational support perceived by them can persuade to support their institution to meet its goals.

Similarly, Peng, et al (2022), conducted a study on the connection linking perceived organizational support (POS) with nurses' professional values in China, with the moderating effect of emotional labor. One of the outcomes in the study meant that perceived organizational support allows nurses to sense positively about their job, that can help in the formation of professional attitudes and behaviors. In the Philippine context, separate studies were done regarding perceived organizational support and professional values. Sosas and Gosiengfiao (2021), found out that hospital nurses in Bacolod City apply professional values regularly, which could mean that despite the challenges they face, they have a high regard for the practice of professional values. On the other hand, Labrague, et al. (2018), focused on perceived organizational support and its effect on job outcomes of nurses. They found out that nurses working in government hospitals had lesser levels of perceived organizational support (POS) than those working in private hospitals.

Building on these findings, the study is unique from earlier research because of its distinct context and practical applicability—a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga that serves several provinces and frequently faces staffing issues and overcrowding. The study directly investigated the relationship between professional values and perceived organizational support (POS) in a high-pressure government hospital setting, whereas previous studies (Peng et al., 2022; Sosas & Gosiengfiao, 2021; Labrague et al., 2018) separately examined these two variables. This study is grounded by these studies and is inspired by the personal experiences of the researcher during her clinical internship and the experiences of the staff nurses.

Currently, the bed capacity of the hospital is still limited compared to its catchment area. Some wards in the hospital need to accommodate twice of its bed capacity to cater all patients who are admitted and needing further medical management. This is the reality even prior to pandemic. Therefore, the accessibility of hospital beds is not only an issue to patients so they w receive services from the hospital, but it is also a concern to health professionals like nurses on how they can deliver safe and effective patient care. Additionally, some nurses feel that trainings are more on skills, losing focus on psychosocial wellness programs that can help the staff nurses thrive in work stress and burnout. In fact, the practice of cascading of training learnings from participants to their colleagues is not widely implemented. While there is an effort to make partnership with other schools, training and development of staff, monthly rewards and recognition, the hospital is not spared of problems like understaffing, burnout, and attrition of staff.

In fact, based on data from the Department of Health (as cited by Porcalla, 2023), there are approximately 124,000 registered nurses in the Philippines who are either unemployed or underemployed. There are nurses who are still working in the private and government hospital that are exhausted and not sufficiently paid. Hence, due to the insufficient institutional support, Filipino nurses always feel dissatisfied with their work and will be forced to leave (Labrague, et al., 2018).

Moreover, the nurse-to-patient ratio in the Philippines starts with 1:20 and can increase up to 1:50. By far, this exceeds the recommended nurse-to-patient ratio according to Department of Health (Villanueva, 2023). Some nurses in the hospital no longer lament about workload itself due to disparities in nurse-to-patient ratio, but they cry of the effects of being overworked – such as the lack of nurse-patient interaction

and being prone to possible errors. Even with the presence of safety huddles and policies (e.g. no recapping, medication safety, handwashing etc.) to enhance quality of patient care, nurses lose the chance of building rapport and in becoming patient advocates. Given these realities, nurses feel that the hospital can still enhance opportunities to provide more support to improve patient outcomes. For them, this support may come in the form of improving distribution of work, inclusion of technology in documentation as this reduces paperworks, more regularized employees for better pay and job security, wellness programs, resilience trainings and a look at “*kamustahan*” sessions to show there is caring for the carers.

Ultimately, concerns regarding patient safety and comfort are raised by these problems, which include understaffing, the need for hospital expansion, and the staff's wish for more in-person check-ins from their superiors. These elements might emphasize the necessity of stronger organizational support and the role that professional values play in providing high-quality care. Although these difficulties may be unique to the tertiary government hospital in Pampanga where the study was conducted, they also represent more general issues in similar establishments. The study may produce results that are applicable and pertinent to the larger nursing workforce because of the hospital's larger service population than other hospitals.

Thus, the goal of this research is to determine the correlation between the perceived organizational support (POS) and the professional values of staff nurses.

Statement of the Problem

Despite efforts to understand the impact of perceived organizational support to the development of professional values, there is still lack of comprehensive understanding about it, especially in the Philippine setting. This research was intended

to determine the correlation between the perceived organizational support and the professional values of staff nurses working in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine the correlation between the perceived organizational support and professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. This study aimed to assess the perceived organizational support, evaluate the professional values, analyze the correlation between these variables and provide evidence-based recommendations in the future on how to enhance organizational support to reinforce the use of professional values by staff nurses. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of perceived organizational support (POS) of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga?
2. What is the level of professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga in terms of:
 - 2.1 Activism
 - 2.2 Caring
 - 2.3 Professionalism
3. Is there a significant correlation between the perceived organizational support (POS) and the professional values of staff nurses working in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga?

Significance of the Study

This study on staff nurses' perceived organizational support and professional values is of great benefit as this addressed the lack or limited studies conducted about this, especially in government hospitals in the Philippines. Furthermore, the findings of this study will be valuable to the following:

Hospital Administration. This provides appropriate feedback to the hospital management regarding the importance of providing strong organizational support to their staff. With the results of the study, the hospital may develop a framework that will provide a sustainable support to the staff nurses.

Staff Nurses. This provides essential information that can help nurses embrace professional values as guiding principles in their practice, thereby enhancing the quality of care they deliver.

Patients. They are directly be affected from the bearing of perceived organizational support (POS) to professional values. A supportive environment with value-aligned staff nurses leads to improved better patient outcomes.

Nursing Administration. The importance of studying the nurses' perceived organizational support and professional values lies in the ability to foster a supportive and values-driven environment for nurses which can support the implementation of policy on the practice of company core values in rendering service to patients. The results of this study may inform the development of strategies that strengthen organizational support and enhance nursing practice.

Nursing Education. The importance of organizational support and having value-driven nurses may be reinforced in the clinical setting. Nurse educators can emphasize

not only the importance of technical competencies but also the applicability of professional values in practice.

Future Studies. Further research on perceived organizational support (POS) and professional values within the Philippine setting would be highly valuable, given the current scarcity of literature on these topics.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study was focused on perceived organizational support and the professional values of staff nurses and the correlation of these variables. As individuals, nurses are humans who are unique from one another; however, there is a likelihood that individual characteristics like age will affect the perception on organizational support and the application of professional values. In this study, most of the participants were relatively young, which added to the limits of this study. The study did not compare scores between demographic characteristics.

Chapter II

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Literature

Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived organizational support (POS) is an individual's view of the magnitude to which an organization values his or her contribution, gives support and regards about their welfare. Whenever workers are in a disruptive situation, the organization acts as an assurance that support and assistance will be given through the provision of the right solutions (Sabir, et al., 2022; Setyoko, et al., 2022; Sheikh, 2023). It is an illustration of an organization where an employee works and sees how he or she is valued and supported because of his or her performance and efforts (Setyoko, et al., 2022; Riska, et al., 2023; Sheikh, 2023). POS can be attributed to how a person shows commitment to the organization (Putri, et al., 2023; Patnaik, et al., 2023).

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is measured by four factors, namely: organizational care factor, positive/negative supervisor interactions, leader member exchange and support reward system. The organizational care factor fine points how much the employee feels that the organization really cares for him or her. While the positive/negative supervisor interactions deal with the good and bad encounters between the employee and the supervisor. The leader member exchange refers to the sense of the employee - if he or she belongs to those most-liked and thought-of by his or her superiors, and lastly, the support reward system factor that focuses on the encouragement and recognition that employees need for jobs well-done (The Workforce Insiders, 2019).

However, in a conceptual study conducted by Yogeswaran (2020), different factors of perceived organizational support were traced based on studies conducted from the year 1997 to 2017. Some of these factors are leader-member exchange, satisfaction with pay system, working conditions, supervisor support, organizational rewards and procedural justice, career opportunities, fairness, etc.

Perceived organizational support (POS) sums up the overall happiness and contribution of employees about their organization. When the organization values and supports the employees' emotions, work, material and values, the employees tend to be more loyal and engaged (All Answers Ltd., 2018). Studies concerning perceived organizational support (POS) have shown a strong connection and relationship with work performance, lesser burnout and stress, stronger organizational commitment and job satisfaction (Kurtessis et. al., 2017; Kumar & Ansari, 2020; Rockstuhl et. al. 2020). Previous research about POS within the pandemic time frame found out that an alteration in the working environment or working conditions had a positive effect on employees' perception of organizational support (Pagnucci et. al.,2021; Allah, 2020; Feldman, 2021; Irish Nurses and Midwives Organisation, 2021).

Varying Factors in Perceived Organizational Support

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) shows employees' belief that their company gives importance to their contributions and well-being, reinforced by equality, sympathetic leadership, and HR practices, especially when perceived as optional choices. Fair process, relating transparency and worker feedback, is strongly linked to POS. Sympathetic leadership, including transformational leadership, boosts POS by exemplifying organizational values and forming a trickle-down effect where superiors who feel supported extend support to subordinates. Under the concept of POS,

leaders may be trained on supportive ways to address staff errors. Research highlights POS' continued significance across cultures and time and in spite evolving workplace dynamics, POS remains a universal and enduring concept (Eisenberger et al., 2020).

Since the introduction of the term perceived organizational support in 1986, it has caught a lot of attention through research. Elaborating on the study conducted by Yogeswaran (2020), key studies about perceived organizational support showed different factors included in it. Earlier study made by Wayne, et al. in 1997 (as cited by Yogeswaran, 2020) suggested that leader-member exchange affects an employee's perceived organizational support and that there exists an exchange relationship between superiors and employees. The underlying principle of the leader-member exchange concept is that leaders eventually form a diverse relationship between them and their subordinates and this could range from low to high quality (Aggarwal et al, 2020).

Still part of the reviews made by Yogeswaran (2020), a study made by Mulvey and team in 2000 recognized the impact of pay satisfaction to the perceived organizational support of employees. Subsequently, Rhoades and others, including with Eisenberger were able to connect supervisor support and other positive treatments received by employees like fairness, rewards, and good working conditions with perceived organizational support. Other past studies made by Weiliu, Eisenberger and Stinglhamber in the years 2004 and 2011 (as cited by Yogeswaran, 2020), stated that appropriate human resource practices and policies can also be related to perceived organizational support. That is when employees feel secured with their jobs through the provision of policies and training, they tend to have positive perceived organizational support.

Nurses' Perceived Organizational Support

Nursing jobs are of high risk and of heavy workload. If and when nurses have perceived positive organizational support and see that they are valued at work, they will be inspired to commit themselves to work and care about the progress of the organization (Liu & Liu, 2016). Nurses have identified three precursors leading to the presence of organizational support. These three precursors are the first-line managers, overarching organization and the college. First-line managers refer to the direct supervisors, overarching organization represents the middle and upper management and lastly, the college includes colleagues, other departments and wards (Gadolin, 2021).

Perceived organizational support is proven to have remarkable effect on nursing practice. Nurses' perceived organizational support in Egypt were found to have a highly significant correlation with their autonomy to make decisions in their units (Saad & Elsayed, 2019). Even with moderate levels of perceived organizational support, the psychological resilience of nurses in Turkey during the COVID-19 pandemic was improved (Karadas, Dogu & Oz, 2022). POS is also found to be effective in the ability of nurses to handle and resolve ethical conflicts. Nurses who experience positive perceived organizational support, find meaning and joy in their work (Nilsson, et al., 2023). Similarly, Wang, et al., (2022), concluded in their study that POS played a significant role in reducing workplace stress that in return, reduces insomnia among nurses. Likewise, the study conducted by Pertiwi et al., (2019) concluded that nurses' perception on organizational support shows a vital role in their work performance.

Even a few recent studies that showed lower levels of perceived organizational support (POS) on nurses, have proven the importance of POS at work. Robaee

(2018), found out in their study that nurses in Tehran had low scores on perceived organizational support and high levels of moral distress.

Organizational Support for Nurses in the Hospital Setting

Hospitals can support nurses in various ways that address both their professional and personal well-being. These include addressing mental health issues, acknowledging their contributions, offering professional development opportunities, and creating a supportive work environment (Martin-Ferreres et al., 2021). Specifically, nurses will feel supported by their superiors and colleagues by fostering a sense of teamwork and good camaraderie. When nurses feel involved in decision-making and are able to open their ideas freely, they are able to participate in building their team. Additionally, mentorship programs can help the nurses to have access to well-seasoned nurses that can inspire them (Teamwork in Nursing: Team-Building Strategies for Better Patient Care, 2024).

The support for nurses abroad is often better than locally. Often, these nurses receive better pay, conducive benefits and healthier working environment. Numerous avenues, such as professional associations, networks, and initiatives aimed at meeting their needs and advancing their well-being, are available to support nurses employed overseas. These support networks assist nurses in advocating for their rights, exchanging resources and knowledge, and gaining access to career advancement opportunities (Hospital Management Asia, 2024; Philippine Daily Inquirer, 2018).

Nurses' Well Being

Nurses, patients, healthcare organizations, and society are all impacted by

nurses' well-being—or lack thereof (Flaubert et al., 2021). Individual nurses' physical and mental health, sense of fulfillment and joy in their work, professional satisfaction, and job engagement are all impacted by well-being. Patients' opinions of the quality of care they receive are impacted by nurses' well-being (McClelland, 2017).

A person's assessment of the psychological, social, and physical resources required to overcome a social, psychological, or physical obstacle is all part of the intrinsically complicated concept of well-being. An established definition of well-being is adopted in the 2019 National Academies Report Taking Action Against Clinician Burnout. An all-encompassing idea that describes quality of life in relation to a person's health and environmental, organizational, and psychosocial aspects of their job. The experience of favorable opinions and the existence of supportive environments both within and outside of the workplace that allow employees to flourish and realize their full potential is known as well-being. Professional well-being is linked to people's job satisfaction, which includes feeling involved, finding purpose and fulfillment in their work (Flaubert, 2021).

According to the American Nurses Association, ethical dilemmas could result in moral suffering, such as moral distress or moral injury, as these are faced by nurses in all positions and environments (Rushton, 2018). Moral distress arises and nurses' integrity is threatened when they are unable to act on their moral decisions due to internal or external limitations (Ulrich & Grady, 2018). Additionally, moral uncertainty, moral conflicts or dilemmas involving conflicting ethical values or commitments, or tensions resulting from the inability to communicate moral concerns to others can all cause moral distress to differing degrees (Morley et al., 2019). The most thoroughly studied type of moral suffering, moral distress, is brought on by moral adversity that

compromises or goes against a person's integrity and professional values (Flaubert, 2021).

Professional Values

Professional values serve as benchmark for individuals to follow in the conduct of their careers. These are important in promoting the right behavior, enhancing work productivity and developing a positive working environment (Salveron, 2023). These are the core principles that employees exhibit in their workplace. These professional values can be in the form of actions, skills, and behaviors that organizations want to see in an employee (Kirova, 2023). Professional groups have a set of accepted standards of practice that are being used to assess the capacity of an individual or organization and reinforce individual identity and performance (Weis & Schank, 2009).

In the healthcare context, there are many ethical concerns, which makes the use of values in the profession as important in order to render excellent health care services (Alabdulaziz et al., 2021; Alsufyani et al., 2022).

Nursing Professional Values

Kaya et al. (2017) stated that professional values serve as the basis for nursing practice as nurses can apply what they have learned in school. Having the guidance to act morally at work provides nurses the opportunity to have patient interaction, complete care, and collaboration with co-workers, management and other members of the healthcare team. The first tool to measure nurses' professional values was developed by Weis and Schank (Weis & Schank, 2000). It was later transformed into Nurses Professional Values Scale - Revised (NPVS-R) (Weis & Schank, 2009) and further developed into the Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3 (NPVS-3) (Weis &

Schank, 2017). NPVS—3 is focused on measuring the professional values of nurses based on three dimensions: activism, caring and professionalism. Activism refers to the actions of nurses to maintain and improve their profession, publicly and globally. Caring pertains to the desire of nurses to render whole care to all their patients without bias. On the other hand, professionalism is reflected on nurses' development through self-assessment and continuous learning (Alsufyani et al., 2022).

In the study conducted by Poorchangizi et al. (2019), nursing students from Iran showed that they have high regard to patient confidentiality and privacy while they scored low on some professional values about participation in decision-making pertaining to distribution of resources. These results suggested the importance of the role of educators in emphasizing the importance of values to nursing practice. Moreover, the need for educational involvements that not only teach the importance of patient-centered care but also promote an understanding of the broader ethical considerations that warrants the use of professional values in nursing practice.

Furthermore, in the study of Poreddi et al. (2021), nurses in India found the values under the domain for caring as more necessary over the values under activism and professionalism. Although this is an indication that there is a strong commitment to caring for patients, it also emphasized the potential gaps on other aspects of professional values like professionalism and activism. Then, despite the acknowledgement of these values, challenges persist in applying them into practice. Abdulaziz (2021) laid emphasis on this issue, signifying a disconnection between theoretical understanding and the practical application in the nursing profession.

Dimensions of Nurses Professional Values: Caring, Activism, Professionalism

The first factor which is Caring, is the center of nursing practice and it was taken

from the first three provisions of the 2015 American Nurses Association Code of Ethics. These three provisions concern with pledge to individuals or families, their protection of health and nursing practice. Activism, the second factor, is related to the provisions like advancement in the profession and prioritization of health globally. Particularly, Activism is focused on social roles of the nursing profession and its accountability on public health. Lastly, Professionalism, which includes provisions on giving leadership, ethical and valuable care in an environment that is safe (Weis & Schank, 2017).

Additionally, the first three provisions of the American Nurses Association Code of Ethics (2015) details how caring is essential to nursing practice. These provisions revolve around respecting the individual, his dignity and staying committed to protect him with his rights, health, and safety. Similarly, the Code of Ethics for Registered Nurses in the Philippines tells the same. The nurses are expected to take appropriate steps in safeguarding the rights and benefits of patients (Professional Regulation Commission, n.d). By recognizing the worth of each patient and striving to meet their needs holistically, nurses are able to maintain the essential principles of their profession. However, the trend in rendering patient care is now highly complex and sometimes would lack the caring substance (Karlsson & Pennbrant, 2020). The ethical caring mantra – “I was there, I saw, I witnessed, and I became responsible”, can be helpful on realizing how to take good care of patients (Eriksson, 2018).

Activism is another aspect of measuring the use of professional values in nursing practice. This is focused on advancing the nursing profession and advocating for priorities in global health (Weis & Schank, 2017). Because of the concrete experiences of nurses, they become keys to influencing and determining public health policies,

health related social needs and advocate for global health equity (Duquesne University School of Nursing Online, 2022). Just like the call of Dr. Ernest Grant – president of the American Nurses Association (ANA), for nurses to consider becoming involved in developing public health policies (Goodyear, 2022). There are several ways on how nurses can elevate and show commitment to the nursing profession - which can be through joining professional associations, continuing education, mentoring new nurses and continue to project professionalism. Nurses' engagement to these advocacies demonstrate assurance to advancing the nursing profession and improving global health (Sinclair, 2020). Additionally, Haddad & Geiger (2023), gave emphasis on the provisions of the ANA Code of Ethics as guidelines to making ethical considerations, one of which is the provision that states -- nurses should work collaboratively within the discipline and other healthcare professionals to maintain the concept of "health for all individuals".

Lastly, professionalism, which is equally important as the other domains in measuring professional values, is defined by the American Nurses Association (as cited by Mozaparifour, 2024) as providing high quality care to patients while maintaining professional values like integrity, accountability and responsibility. When nurses demonstrate professional manners, patients are able to receive improved care, communication is better across all members of the healthcare team and positive work environment is achieved. Moreover, professionalism includes not only following guiding principles and evidence-based practices but also promoting safety, quality improvement and collaboration for better patient outcomes.

Collaboration among nurses for better patient outcomes is measured through peer review, as mentioned in one of the survey items of the Nurses Professional

Values Scale (Weis & Schank, 2017). Peer review is defined as the process of evaluating the nursing care rendered by other nurses through consultation and collaboration. This ensures that there is increased in accountability and nursing practice is constantly regulated (Foster, 2018).

Under the guidelines of Article III – Registered Nurses and Practice, the nurses must be aware of the scope of practice and meet the standards in rendering patient care. The nurses must keep themselves updated to have the competencies in knowledge, skills, and attitude. Also, awareness of the duties and responsibilities in the practice of nursing profession is necessary as defined by the “Philippine Nursing Act of 2002 and the implementing rules and regulations (Professional Regulation Commission, n.d).

Synthesis

Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is the level to which nurses perceive to be appreciated and nurtured within their institution. Within high-pressure healthcare settings, this perception of support plays a great role in encouraging nurses' motivation and commitment to work. Where supervisors and institutions show concern for their workers, it enables professional development and strengthens core values. Eisenberger et al. (1986) highlight that employees who feel a lot of support are more likely to work harder and identify strongly with their organization's goals. Regrettably, most of the staff nurses indicate inadequate support, which may produce emotional exhaustion and moral distress. On the other hand, strong POS has been found to boost core professional values like compassion, advocacy, and professionalism. An appreciative work environment not only favors the nurses but also leads to enhanced patient care outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

Organizational Support Theory

This study was anchored on the Organizational Support Theory (OST), which posits that individuals develop perceived organizational support (POS), that their superiors have a positive or negative regard towards them. The theory originated from social exchange theory (Maan et. al., 2020). In the social exchange between the superiors and subordinates, it reflects the concern of the organization based on the subordinates' perception. POS is significant because it is connected to job attitude and behavior (Paul, 2020). As a result, perceived organizational support affects employee performance. When employees feel the support and care from the organization, the organization addresses their concerns and needs, which in return enhances the performance of employees. In the healthcare setting, when nurses have enhanced performance, they deliver quality patient care.

Perceived organizational support (POS) has been found to be beneficial to work performance and affect emotional labor and the development of professional values (Peng, 2022). This is relative to the organizational support theory (OST), wherein POS triggers a social exchange process. The employees are obliged to help their organization achieve its goals and objectives and expect that their organization will increase efforts to give greater rewards. In this study, the participants' level of perceived organizational support and professional values were measured by the researcher using standardized tools.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the study consisted of the variables – perceived

organizational support and professional values. The present study aimed to find out the correlation between perceived organizational support and professional values of staff nurses.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Correlation between Perceived Organizational Support and Professional Values.

This conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between perceived organizational support and the professional values of staff nurses. In this study, perceived organizational support is the independent variable, while professional values acted as the dependent variable. The levels of both variables were measured using the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and the Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3 (NPVS-3), respectively. The framework is represented by a connecting arrow line between the two variables, signifying the hypothesized correlation. Specifically, the study examined whether higher levels of perceived organizational support were associated with higher levels of professional values – namely activism, caring, and professionalism – among staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. The analysis sought to determine the strength and direction of this association, exploring whether changes in the independent variable (perceived organizational support) corresponded consistently with changes in the dependent variable (professional values).

Operational Definition of Terms

For the purpose of this study, the following terms are defined operationally:

Perceived Organizational Support (POS). This refers to the staff nurses' subjective perception of how much the hospital values their contributions and cares about their well-being. This includes the institution's support for personal and professional development, the cultivation of a positive work environment, the provision of fair treatment, and the acknowledgment of nurses' efforts and achievements.

Professional Values. These are the guiding principles and ethical standards that influence nurses' clinical decisions and behavior in practice. This encompasses core values such as advocacy, accountability, human dignity, integrity, and altruism as manifested in their roles and responsibilities.

Activism. A dimension of professional values that pertains to nurses' active engagement in promoting global and community health. This includes participation in health advocacy, influencing policy, collaborating with other health professionals, conducting, or supporting nursing research, and applying evidence-based practices.

Caring. This refers to the nurse's commitment to deliver compassionate and holistic care. It includes respecting patients' rights, confidentiality, privacy, and safety, as well as advocating for high standards of care and addressing inappropriate practices by other healthcare providers.

Professionalism. This dimension involves the pursuit of excellence in nursing practice through continuous self-improvement, lifelong learning, ethical behavior, and assuming responsibility for one's professional growth and well-being.

Patients. Individuals receiving healthcare services in the inpatient or outpatient departments of the hospital. They represent a diverse group in terms of demographics, clinical conditions, and care needs.

Staff Nurses. Registered nurses employed at the selected tertiary government hospital in Pampanga who are assigned to clinical areas and are primarily engaged in direct bedside or patient care.

Tertiary Hospital. A government-owned healthcare institution offering specialized diagnostic, therapeutic, and rehabilitative services. It serves as the primary setting for this research study.

Research Hypothesis

HO₁: There is a significant correlation between perceived organizational support and professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga.

Chapter III

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

In this study, a correlational research design will be employed to investigate the relationship between perceived organizational support and its impact on professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. A correlational design often used in research, is a methodological approach that investigates the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. This design seeks to determine the strength and direction of a relationship, if any, to understand how variables change together (Browner et al., 2023; Creswell & Poth, 2018). This design was chosen for its effectiveness in determining the degree and direction of association between two variables without manipulating the study environment (Grove & Gray, 2019; Stangor, 2015). By analyzing naturally occurring relationships, the research aimed to uncover whether a positive perception of support from the organization correlated with stronger professional values among nurses. The correlational approach allowed for the collection of quantitative data through the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3 (NPVS-3), enabling the researchers to measure the level of perceived support and the prevalence of professional values within the staff nurses.

The implementation of this design involved the distribution of Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3 (NPVS-3) to a representative sample of staff nurses within a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. Statistical analysis, such as Spearman rho correlation analysis, was utilized to examine the correlation between perceived organizational support and

professional values. This analysis helped identify significant correlations and offered insights into the potential impact of organizational support on staff nurses' professional values.

Research Setting

This study was conducted in a tertiary government hospital, that caters to the people of Pampanga and nearby provinces like Nueva Ecija, Bataan, Bulacan, Zambales, Tarlac and Aurora. Under its license to operate with the Department of Health (DOH), it is implementing 850 bed capacity, its actual bed capacity is 920 while it has an approved 1000 bed capacity for ongoing structures. It is a Level III teaching and training hospital and a leading healthcare organization in Central Luzon, it envisions to be an end-referral multi-specialty hospital in Region III. It renders a wide range of medical services such as Emergency Medicine, General Surgery (such as excision/incision biopsy, thyroidectomy, repair of trachea and esophagus, mastectomy, appendectomy, limb amputation, creation of AV shunt etc), Internal Medicine (such as cardiovascular, endocrine, gastroenterology, hematology, infectious diseases, etc), Obstetrics and Gynecology, Ophthalmology, Pediatrics, Otorhinolaryngology and Orthopaedics. Under the Nursing Service are the different nursing units – Clinical Nursing Units, Operating Room, Special Care Areas, Obstetrics Complex, Labor Room, Obstetrical OR/CS OR, PACU, Out-Patient Department and Hemodialysis Unit.

Sampling Technique

The population for this study comprised of staff nurses working in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga, who were interacting with patients, organizational systems, and policies daily. These individuals provided direct patient care and

represented a diverse group with varying degrees of experience, specialization, and interaction with the hospital's organizational support structures. Given the hospital's role as a primary healthcare provider in the region, the nursing staff encountered a wide range of clinical situations and varying work demands, making their perceptions of organizational support and its impact on their professional values particularly relevant for this study. The focus on this specific population aimed to provide insights into how perceived organizational support within a tertiary hospital setting influenced the professional values of nurses, including their commitment to patient care, ethical practices, and advocacy for patient and professional nursing standards.

Inclusion Criteria:

This study included the staff nurses working at the bedside holding permanent positions and those who expressed their willingness to participate through informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria:

This criterion covered those who hold managerial or supervisory positions and staff nurses who refused to join in the study due to circumstances that they deemed fit, like the five (5) staff nurses who were on maternity leave, two (2) staff nurses who were on vacation leave, two (2) staff nurses who submitted their resignation during the data collection, two (2) staff nurses refused to participate in the study and one (1) staff nurse on training during the data collection.

The population size of staff nurses considered in this study were 481, comprising 278 staff nurses with Nurse I position and 203 staff nurses in the Nurse II position. These staff nurses came from various departments namely: Emergency Department,

Internal Medicine, Surgery, Pediatrics, Outpatient Department, Payward, Obstetrics/Gynecology, Obstetrics/Neonatal Intensive Care Unit, Operating Room-Post Anesthesia Care Unit, Hemodialysis Unit and Employee Health and Wellness Clinic.

A minimum required sample size (n) of 153 was needed to be able to detect a significant correlation coefficient of at least 0.2, with 95% confidence and 80% statistical power. This sample size was computed using G*Power version 3.1.9.7. However, to account for possible refusals or withdrawals in participation, an additional of 20% (approximately $n = 31$) was added for a total target sample size of $n = 184$. At the end of this study, 172 staff nurses participated in the data collection. Figure 2 shows the G*Power output for the sample size calculation.

Figure 2. G*Power output for Sample Size

The sample size of 184 was divided proportionally among the Nurse I and Nurse

II, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Population and Sample Size for the Study

Position Title of Staff Nurses	Population Size	Computed Sample Size	Actual Sample Size to be Used (with buffer)
Nurse I	278	88	106
Nurse II	203	65	78
TOTAL	481	153	184

To obtain the 184 nurse participants, the researcher utilized stratified random sampling technique in the following manner:

1. The researcher requested the Nursing Service of the hospital to prepare the list of the 481 staff nurses, with the Nurse I staff numbered consecutively from 1 to 278 and the Nurse II staff numbered 1 to 203.
2. The researcher used a random number generator to obtain 106 random numbers for the Nurse I participants and 78 random numbers for the Nurse II participants.
3. A research assistant coordinated with the Nursing Service on how to invite the nurses in the list (with assigned numbers corresponding to the randomly generated numbers) to participate in the study.

Data Collection

Data collection was done through the administration of online survey questionnaires. Data from perceived organizational support (POS) was measured

using Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS) and Professional Values was measured using the Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3.

Procedures

Figure 3. Flow of conduct of the study.

The data gathering procedures for the study on perceived organizational support and its impact on professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga was meticulously planned to ensure the collection of accurate and comprehensive information as shown in Figure 3.

The researcher initially secured a written permission to conduct the study from the designated setting through the Chief Nurse. Following this, the research proposal was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee for review and formal approval. Upon obtaining ethical clearance, the researcher enlisted a research assistant to facilitate informational sessions with the nursing staff. These sessions aimed to explain the purpose of the study, highlight the significance of their voluntary participation, and assure them of the confidentiality of their responses—key factors in fostering trust and encouraging honest engagement. Prior to these sessions, the researcher ensured that the research assistant was thoroughly oriented on the study protocol, the informed consent process, and the data collection instruments to be utilized.

Upon receiving approval to conduct the research study from the Medical Center Chief and the Chief Nurse, the researcher adhered to the following research protocols:

First, following the approval of the research study, a copy of the proposal was submitted to the Research Ethics Committee (REC) of the study setting. An endorsement letter from the Chief Nurse was secured and addressed to the unit heads, and a letter of permission was sent to the developers of the research tools used in the study. The researcher oriented the research assistant regarding the study's purpose, informed consent procedures, data collection methods, and the proper handling and turnover of collected data. Confidentiality and anonymity were

emphasized, with each signed consent form securely folded and sealed in an envelope.

Second, after receiving authorization to proceed, the researcher coordinated with the Nursing Service Department to prepare a list of eligible participants. The research assistant then conducted short information sessions lasting 5 to 10 minutes during the participants' monthly unit meetings to avoid disrupting their duty hours. During these sessions, the study was explained, and informed consent was obtained. Each participant who agreed to take part in the study received a copy of the informed consent form.

Third, with the help of the research assistant, the survey questionnaires were explained to the participants. Instructions were provided to access the online survey through a QR code or link included in their informed consent form. Participants were encouraged to complete the survey at a time and place convenient and safe for them, ensuring the privacy and confidentiality of their responses. Although participants were not required to respond immediately, they were given one week to complete the survey. This timeframe ensured that participants had sufficient opportunity to provide thoughtful responses while allowing the researcher to manage the data collection period effectively. The estimated time to complete both questionnaires was 10 to 15 minutes.

Participation was limited to this one-time engagement, with no follow-up interviews, observations, or additional tasks required.

Since each nursing unit holds monthly meetings on varying schedules, these gatherings served as the optimal time to engage potential participants. Considering both the unit meeting schedules and the availability of the research assistant, the

entire data collection was conducted within a two-month period. All participants were surveyed within this timeframe, ensuring that the data collection occurred in a relatively close and consistent manner.

To minimize potential bias and ensure objectivity, the research assistant—rather than the researcher—was assigned to explain the study, secure informed consent, and address participants' questions or concerns. Given that the researcher is a nurse leader from another hospital, direct involvement in data collection could have influenced participant responses due to perceived authority or pressure to participate. This potential influence is associated with the *Hawthorne Effect*, where individuals alter their behavior when they are aware of being observed (Daniel, 2023).

Lastly, after completing data collection, the researcher downloaded the survey responses from the online platform and saved them in a spreadsheet application. All identifying information was removed to ensure anonymity before the data were forwarded to a professional statistician for analysis.

Research Instruments

The personal information of the participants such as the age, sex, educational attainment and length of stay/work in the hospital was collected as part of the online survey questionnaires. The research instruments were accessed through online platform either using the link or QR code provided to each participant.

The first instrument of the study, the Survey of Perceived Organizational Support (SPOS), is designed to assess how leaders in the nursing profession feel their employers value and support them. This ten-item scale, created by Eisenberger (2021), has been extensively used in organizational research to measure how much

workers feel their employers care about them and their contributions. The Likert-style scale has seven points, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 7 (strongly agree), giving the staff nurses a wide range of options for expressing their opinions. For the purpose of this study, the researcher has categorized the scores into two levels – scores greater than 4 were considered high and scores below 4 were considered low. Total scores range from 10 to 70. Higher scores indicate higher levels of perceived organizational support. All items are outlined in a positive manner.

In addition, Instrument 1 was used in research by Maan et al. in 2020 lends credence to its validity and precision. In addition to providing a rationale for using the SPOS, this research offers empirical backing for the method's efficacy. One of the SPOS items in the research by Maan et al. had an impressively high degree of reliability consistency (0.88), demonstrating the scale's dependability in reflecting head nurses' opinions of organizational support, after obtaining a validity index of 4.82. This further strengthens the reliability of the instrument, increasing faith in its potential to provide useful insights into how staff nurses rate the assistance they get from their healthcare organizations. Instrument 1 (the SPOS) is a thorough and well-validated measure for assessing a key feature of the healthcare work environment, which aids in the evaluation of the study aims. SPOS was used on several studies involving nurses, particularly its 8-item version (Pertwi et al. ,2020; Robaee et al., 2018).

Moreover, Instrument 2 (Nurses Professional Values Scale - 3) is an essential instrument for evaluating the professional values of staff nurses. It is taken from the American Nurses Association's code of ethics, which measures nurses' values on Activism, Caring and Professionalism dimensions. The NPVS-3 is 28-item instrument, and every sentence is accompanied with a five-point Likert scale, from 1 (not

important) to 5 (most important). Each item is positively stated and none of the sentences is negatively stated. Under the domain of Caring are the items 2, 3, 14, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 21 and 22. In the domain Activism are the items 10, 11, 12, 13, 17, 23, 24, 25, 26 and 27. And lastly, included in the domain Professionalism are items 1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, and 28. In this study, scores were categorized by the researcher using predetermined thresholds. Scores above 3 were considered high while scores below 3 were considered low. The range of scores can possibly be from 28 to 140. The higher the score, the greater is the degree of alignment of nurses to professional values (Weis & Schank, 2017).

Research by Asiandi et al. in 2021 demonstrates NPVS-3 dependability and appropriateness, further supporting its use. The study, which included participants from Indonesia, has confirmed reliability (0.97) and validity resulting from 0.49 to 0.84 of the instruments for measuring Activism, Caring and Professionalism dimensions. The dependability of the NPVS-3 gives researchers more confidence in using it as a valid assessment instrument.

To ensure validity and reliability of the instruments, a permission letter to utilize these questionnaires was forwarded to the developers.

Plan for Data Analysis

Frequency and percent distributions was used to summarize the actual responses per item in the instruments for perceived organizational support and for professional values. Mean responses per item was also computed. On the other hand, for the summed scores for perceived organizational support and for professional values, the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum observed values was obtained. These statistics provided an overall picture of how staff nurses perceive

organizational support and the prominence of professional values within the nursing staff. Moreover, these statistics served as bases for the identification of general trends in perceptions and values among the nurses, highlighting areas of strength and potential improvement in organizational support.

For determining the correlation between the study variables, Spearman’s rho correlation coefficient was computed. This was able to indicate the strength of correlation and direction of correlation (either positive, meaning direct correlation or negative, meaning inverse correlation) between summed scores of perceived organizational support and professional values. Interpretations of Spearman rho coefficients are as follows (Akoglu, 2018):

Figure 4. Interpretations of Spearman rho coefficients.

Correlation Coefficient		Interpretation
+1	-1	Perfect
+0.9	-0.9	Very Strong
+0.8	-0.8	Very Strong
+0.7	-0.7	Moderate
+0.6	-0.6	Moderate
+0.5	-0.5	Fair
+0.4	-0.4	Fair
+0.3	-0.3	Fair
+0.2	-0.2	Poor
+0.1	-0.1	Poor
0	0	None

Level of significance will be set to $\alpha = 0.05$. A legitimate trial version of the statistical software Stata was requested by the researcher from the official Stata website to facilitate the needed statistical calculations. A summary of the plan for data analysis is presented in the table below:

Table 2*Plan for Data Analysis*

Research Questions	Variables	Type of Data	Statistical Test
1. What is the level of perceived organizational support (POS) of staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga?	Perceived Organizational Support	Interval Data (Summed scores for POS)	Mean, standard deviation
2. What is the level of professional values of staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga in terms of: 2.1 Activism 2.2 Caring 2.3 Professionalism	Professional Values	Interval Data (Summed scores per professional value)	Mean, standard deviation,
3. Is there a significant correlation between the perceived organizational support (POS) and professional values of staff nurses working in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga?	Perceived Organizational Support (IV) and Professional Values (DV)	Interval Data (summed scores)	Spearman rho correlation coefficient

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical standards to protect the rights and welfare of participants. Key ethical considerations included obtaining informed consent, ensuring confidentiality and anonymity, safeguarding privacy, upholding the right to withdraw, and avoiding conflicts of interest. These measures guaranteed that participation—particularly in answering the questionnaires—would not affect the participants' employment status in any way.

Informed Consent. Prior to data collection, written informed consent was obtained from all participants. This consent signified their voluntary agreement to participate after being fully informed about the study's objectives, procedures, potential risks, and benefits. Risks included the possible accidental disclosure of personal information or concerns over low assessment scores impacting employability. To alleviate these concerns, the benefits of participation were emphasized, such as increased awareness of professional values, improved decision-making, refinement of workplace policies, and contributions to a broader understanding of organizational support and professional values. Once consent was granted, participants signed the informed consent form.

Confidentiality and Anonymity. To ensure anonymity, participants were assigned unique codes consisting of letters and numbers in place of their names. All collected data were securely stored, with physical records kept in locked cabinets and digital data protected by password-encrypted files. The research assistant was briefed on the importance of maintaining confidentiality. After the study's completion, results may be shared with the participants, the university, and relevant stakeholders, if participants' identities remain anonymous.

Privacy. Participants' right to privacy was respected throughout the research process. Information shared during the study was used strictly for its intended purpose, and efforts were made to prevent unauthorized access or disclosure.

Right to Withdraw. Participants retained the right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or obligation to provide a reason. Withdrawal could also occur if a participant failed to complete the required surveys or faced significant life changes. More importantly, participation was entirely voluntary and uninfluenced by managerial

or supervisory pressure, and decisions to participate or withdraw had no bearing on the participants' employment status.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher ensured that no conflict of interest influenced the study. There was no financial compensation that might compromise objectivity. While light refreshments and simple tokens of appreciation were offered, these were not intended to sway participation or responses.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Demographic Profile of the Participants

The survey data revealed that the majority of nurse participants (78.5%) were within the age range of 30 to 39 years, with an additional 10.5% belonging to the younger age bracket of 20 to 29 years. These figures suggested that the participant group was relatively young. In terms of gender distribution, females comprised 67.4% of the sample, resulting in a female-to-male ratio of approximately 2:1. Regarding educational attainment, only 9.3% of the respondents had completed postgraduate studies. As for length of service in the government tertiary hospital in Pampanga, nearly half of the participants (49.4%) had been employed there for three years or less, while the remaining 50.6% had more than three years of service. Collectively, these data indicated that the participants were predominantly young, female nurses with varying lengths of service in the institution.

Table 3

Sociodemographic characteristics of study participants

Age	N	%
20-29	18	10.5%
30-39	135	78.5%
40-49	16	9.3%
50-59	3	1.7%
Sex	N	%
Male	56	32.6%
Female	116	67.4%

Educational Attainment		
	n	%
Undergraduate	156	90.7%
Postgraduate	16	9.3%
Years of Stay/work at the research setting		
	N	%
Less than one year	1	0.6%
1 to 3 years	84	48.8%
3 to 10 years	87	50.6%

Perceived Organizational Support

Table 4

Staff Nurses' Perceived Organizational Support

Items	Mean	SD
1. The organization values my contribution to its well-being.	6.00	1.00
2. The organization strongly considers my goal and values.	5.95	1.01
3. Help is available from the organization when I have a problem.	5.88	1.07
4. The organization really cares about my well-being.	5.75	1.19
5. My organization wishes to give me the best possible job for which I am qualified.	6.01	1.06
6. The organization cares about my general satisfaction at work.	5.76	1.20
7. The organization takes pride in my accomplishments at work.	5.80	1.17
8. The organization would forgive an honest mistake on my part.	5.56	1.25

9. The organization is willing to extend itself in order to help me perform my job to the best of my ability.	5.95	1.15
10. The organization cares about my opinions.	5.56	1.29

Descriptive Statistics for the Overall POS Score

Mean: 58.2	Std. Deviation: 10.0	Minimum: 10	Maximum: 70
Median: 60	1 st Quartile: 53.25	3 rd Quartile: 66.00	Interquartile range: 12.75

Table 4 presents the average (mean) score for each item on the POS scale along with the corresponding standard deviations. Additionally, summary statistics for the overall POS score—calculated by summing the Likert-scale responses across all items—are also provided, including the mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, maximum, and quartile values.

The mean scores for all individual items were above 5.5, indicating a generally positive perception of organizational support among the participants. This suggests that, on average, staff nurses in the tertiary-level government hospital in Pampanga feel valued and supported by their employer (Paul, 2020). Response patterns across the Likert scale were consistent, further affirming this positive perception. One notable institutional initiative contributing to this sense of support is the hospital's monthly rewards and recognition program, which helps reinforce the value of nurses within the organization.

Among the items, Item 5 ("My organization wishes to give me the best possible job for which I am qualified.") received the highest mean score ($M = 6.01$, $SD = 1.06$), indicating that nurses strongly believe the organization is invested in their career development and placement. This aligns with findings by Yogeswaran (2020), who emphasized that access to training opportunities enhances employees' perceptions of support. The hospital's consistent provision of free training—including technical skills

(e.g., BLS, ACLS), specialized courses (e.g., Critical Care Nursing), and leadership programs—supports this observation. Similarly, Item 1 ("The organization values my contribution to its well-being.") scored highly ($M = 6.00$, $SD = 1.00$), suggesting that nurses feel their contributions are appreciated. This resonates with the organizational care factor described by The Workforce Insiders (2019), where perceived support is driven by recognition and empathy. During periods of high demand, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, the hospital has demonstrated support through timely salary payments and the hiring of additional staff, further reinforcing this perception. Notably, 50.6% of the participants have served at the hospital for more than three years, reflecting sustained commitment even during challenging times.

Conversely, Items 8 ("The organization would forgive an honest mistake on my part.") and 10 ("The organization cares about my opinions.") received the lowest mean scores (both $M = 5.56$, $SD = 1.25$ and 1.29 , respectively). While still indicating positive sentiments, these results suggest areas where perceptions of organizational support could be strengthened. Item 8 implies that some nurses may feel uncertain about how their mistakes would be treated, while Item 10 points to a potential gap in perceived attentiveness to staff opinions. Supporting literature by Sabir et al. (2022), Setyoko et al. (2022), and Sheikh (2023) highlights the importance of providing reassurance and support during disruptive events, including tolerance for honest mistakes. Eisenberger et al. (2020) also emphasize the need for leaders to be trained in effectively addressing staff errors under the POS framework.

The overall average POS score among participants was 58.2 ($SD = 10.0$). Given that the SPOS uses a 10-item, 7-point Likert scale, total scores can range from 10 to 70. The mean score of 58.2 suggests a high level of perceived organizational support,

although the standard deviation indicates some variability in responses. The lowest recorded score of 10 is a significant outlier and warrants further investigation to understand the underlying causes of such low perceived support. The maximum score of 70 confirms that at least one respondent perceived full support from the organization. The median score of 60, being higher than the mean, suggests a left-skewed distribution, indicating that more respondents scored at the higher end. The first quartile (Q1 = 53.25) and third quartile (Q3 = 66.00) show that 50% of the participants scored between these values, with an interquartile range of 12.75 capturing the central tendency of the group's perceptions.

Professional Values – Caring, Activism and Professionalism

Table 5

Staff Nurses' Professional Values

Caring Dimension	Mean	SD
2. Respect the inherent dignity, values, and human rights of all individuals.	4.59	0.61
3. Protect health and safety of the patient/public.	4.68	0.58
14. Accept responsibility and accountability for own practice.	4.37	0.72
15. Protect moral and legal rights of patients.	4.58	0.63
16. Act as a patient advocate.	4.43	0.69
18. Provide care without bias or prejudice to patients and populations.	4.39	0.70
19. Safeguard patient's right to confidentiality and privacy.	4.59	0.63
20. Confront practitioners with questionable or inappropriate practice.	4.04	0.90
21. Protects rights of participants in research.	4.19	0.78

22. Practice guided by principles of fidelity and respect for person. 4.35 0.69

Descriptive Statistics for the Caring Score

Mean: 44.2 Std. Deviation: 5.4 Minimum: 30 Maximum: 50
 Median: 45 1st Quartile: 41 3rd Quartile: 49 Interquartile range: 8

Activism Dimension	Mean	SD
10. Advance the profession through active involvement in health - related activities.	4.15	0.72
11. Recognize the role of professional nursing associations in shaping health policy.	4.22	0.75
12. Establish collaborative partnerships to reduce healthcare disparities.	4.13	0.73
13. Assume responsibility for meeting health needs of diverse populations.	4.01	0.73
17. Participate in nursing research and/or implement research findings appropriate to practice.	3.85	0.81
23. Actively promote health of populations.	4.28	0.69
24. Participate in professional efforts and collegial interactions to ensure quality care and professional satisfaction.	4.15	0.75
25. Promote mutual peer support and collegial interactions to ensure quality care and professional satisfaction.	4.17	0.74
26. Take action to influence legislators and other policy makers to improve health care.	4.01	0.78
27. Engage in consultation/collaboration to provide optimal care.	4.19	0.71

Descriptive Statistics for the Activism Score

Mean: 41.2 Std. Deviation: 6.2 Minimum: 29 Maximum: 50
 Median: 41 1st Quartile: 37 3rd Quartile: 46 Interquartile range: 9

Professionalism Dimension	Mean	SD
1. Engage in on-going self-evaluation.	4.13	0.71
4. Assume responsibility for personal well-being.	4.35	0.72

5. Participate in peer review.	3.91	0.73
6. Establish standards as a guide for practice.	4.37	0.70
7. Promote and maintain standards where planned learning activities for students take place.	4.17	0.73
8. Initiate actions to improve environments of practice.	4.22	0.67
9. Seek additional education to update knowledge and skills to maintain competency.	4.33	0.69
28. Recognize professional boundaries.	4.39	0.71

Descriptive Statistics for the Professionalism Score

Mean: 33.9	Std. Deviation: 4.5	Minimum: 23	Maximum: 40
Median: 34	1 st Quartile: 32	3 rd Quartile: 37.75	Interquartile range: 5.75

Table 5 presents the mean scores and standard deviations of the participants across the dimensions of Caring, Activism, and Professionalism, which comprise the Nurses' Professional Values. Descriptive statistics—including total mean scores, minimum and maximum values, median, quartiles, and interquartile ranges—were also calculated for each dimension.

Caring Dimension

The Caring dimension reflects core nursing values related to respect, safety, rights, and dignity of patients. Items 3, 2, 19, and 15 received the highest mean scores (≥ 4.58), emphasizing values such as respecting patient dignity, ensuring health and safety, protecting patient rights, and safeguarding confidentiality. This reflects a strong agreement among staff nurses regarding the centrality of caring in their practice.

On the other hand, Items 20 ("Confront practitioners with questionable or inappropriate practice") and 21 ("Protect rights of participants in research") received the lowest mean scores ($M = 4.04$ and 4.19 , respectively; $SD = 0.90$ and 0.78). These responses may suggest discomfort with confronting peers or engaging in ethical

research advocacy. Despite the hospital's implementation of a 360-degree feedback mechanism, staff nurses may feel inhibited in providing candid feedback, especially toward superiors.

The overall mean score for Caring is 44.2 (SD = 5.4) out of a possible 50, reflecting a high level of professional caring values. The range of scores (30–50) indicates that even the lowest scores still represent strong caring tendencies. The median score of 45, slightly higher than the mean, suggests a left-skewed distribution, with more high scores than low ones.

These results affirm that caring remains a foundational value in nursing practice. This aligns with the American Nurses Association (ANA) Code of Ethics (2015) and the Philippine Code of Ethics for Registered Nurses, which assert that nurses must advocate for and protect patients' rights. In practice, this commitment is reinforced through institutional policies, such as the visible posting of the Patients' Bill of Rights in nursing units and patient rooms. Despite high patient workloads, staff nurses at the government tertiary hospital in Pampanga actively engage in safety huddles and other initiatives that prioritize patient well-being.

Activism Dimension

The Activism dimension explores nurses' engagement in professional advocacy and public health efforts. Mean scores for all items ranged from 3.85 to 4.28, indicating that staff nurses place a high level of importance on activism-related values.

Item 23 ("Actively promote health of populations") received the highest mean score (M = 4.28, SD = 0.69), reflecting nurses' strong involvement in public health initiatives. According to Hospital Asia Management (2025), nurses actively participate in

infection control strategies, medical missions, and vaccination drives. Items 24 and 25 also showed high means ($M = 4.15$ and 4.17 ; $SD = 0.75$ and 0.74), demonstrating nurses' strong collaboration in interdisciplinary care and professional networking.

These findings align with the ANA Code of Ethics, which underscores the importance of collaboration and advocacy. Staff nurses demonstrate this through participation in interdisciplinary rounds, structured handovers, and case conferences. Trainings in patient safety and risk management further support these collaborative behaviors. Item 17 ("Participate in nursing research") scored the lowest ($M = 3.85$, $SD = 0.81$), highlighting a relatively lower emphasis on research participation. This may be attributed to clinical demands and high patient loads, which can limit time and motivation for research activities. However, despite these constraints, most nurses completed the study surveys promptly, aided by follow-ups.

Similarly, Item 26 ("Take action to influence legislators") had a lower mean ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.78$), indicating limited engagement in policy advocacy. Hierarchical organizational structures may hinder staff nurses' direct involvement in decision-making processes, as they are primarily focused on patient care responsibilities.

The overall mean score for Activism is 41.2 ($SD = 6.2$) out of a maximum of 50 , indicating a generally high level of activism. The minimum score of 29 still reflects a moderate level of engagement. The median score of 41 equals the mean, suggesting a symmetrical distribution. These results suggest that while nurses value activism, their engagement may vary based on institutional support and structural limitations.

Professionalism Dimension

High mean scores across the Professionalism items indicate a strong emphasis on integrity, accountability, and high standards of care (Mozaparifour, 2024). Top-scoring items include Item 28 (“Recognize professional boundaries”), Item 6 (“Establish standards as a guide for practice”), Item 4 (“Assume responsibility for personal well-being”), and Item 9 (“Seek additional education to update knowledge and skills”), with means ranging from 4.33 to 4.39 and relatively low standard deviations ($SD = 0.69\text{--}0.72$). These reflect staff nurses’ strong commitment to personal and professional development, aligned with Article III of the Philippine Code of Ethics for Nurses (PRC, n.d).

As a tertiary facility, the hospital supports professional growth through a variety of training programs in BLS, ACLS, critical care, and evidence-based practices. However, Item 5 (“Participate in peer review”) received the lowest score ($M = 3.91$, $SD = 0.69$), indicating this aspect of professionalism may be less emphasized. Foster (2018) defines peer review as essential for accountability and self-regulation in nursing. In this context, the relatively lower score could stem from a lack of awareness or perception of peer review as a compliance exercise, rather than a developmental opportunity.

The overall professionalism score averaged 33.9 ($SD = 4.5$) out of a possible 40. The minimum (23) and maximum (40) still reflect a generally high level of professionalism. A median of 34, nearly equal to the mean, suggests a symmetrical distribution like the activism results. This consistency reinforces that professionalism is deeply valued by the staff nurses.

Correlation between the Staff Nurses' Perceived Organizational Support and Professional Values

Table 6

Correlation between the Staff Nurses' Perceived Organizational Support and Professional Values

		POS
CARING	Spearman rho Correlation Coefficient	.352**
	p-value	.000
ACTIVISM	Spearman rho Correlation Coefficient	.442**
	p-value	.000
PROFESSIONALISM	Spearman rho Correlation Coefficient	.356**
	p-value	.000

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 shows the correlation between Staff Nurses' Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and their Professional Values (Caring, Activism, and Professionalism).

The table reveals that all three dimensions of professional values (Caring, Activism, and Professionalism) show statistically significant positive correlations with Perceived Organizational Support (POS). This means that as perceived organizational support increases, staff nurses tend to report higher levels of caring, activism, and professionalism. Conversely, lower perceived organizational support is associated with lower levels of these professional values.

Activism has the strongest correlation with POS (Spearman rho = .442). This suggests that perceived organizational support has the strongest relationship with nurses' engagement in activism-related behaviors and attitudes. While in the study of

Poreddi et al (2021), nurses in a tertiary hospital in India perceived the values under caring domain as more important than activism and professionalism. Caring and Professionalism have fairly strong correlations with POS (Spearman rho = .352 and .356, respectively). Though still significant, these correlations are slightly weaker than that of activism.

The p-values for all correlations are .000, which is far below the .01 significance level. This indicates that these correlations are highly unlikely to be due to chance.

The significant positive correlations highlight the importance of organizational support in fostering positive professional values among staff nurses. When nurses feel supported by their organizations, they are more likely to demonstrate caring, engage in activism, and uphold professional standards. This is consistent with the principles of Organizational Support Theory (OST), which implies that people form perceived organizational support (POS) based on how they believe their superiors regard them (Maan et al., 2020). Stemming from Social Exchange Theory, OST suggests that when nurses perceive positive organizational support, they are more likely to reciprocate by exhibiting positive job attitudes and professional behaviors (Paul, 2020). The stronger correlation between POS and activism suggests that organizations might want to pay particular attention to how their support impacts nurses' willingness to advocate for patients and the profession.

Chapter V

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

This study aimed to determine the perceived organizational support and its impact on the professional values of staff nurses in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga. Specifically, it aimed to describe and determine the following: (1) the level of perceived organizational support of the staff nurses; (2) level of professional values of the staff nurses in terms of activism, caring and professionalism; and (3) the correlation between the perceived organizational support (POS) and the professional values of the staff nurses.

A correlational research design was used to determine the level of perceived organizational support and its impact on the professional values of the 172 staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga. To accurately describe the levels of perceived organizational support and professional values of the staff nurses, mean and standard deviation were used to summarize the responses per item in the survey instruments. While for the summed scores of perceived organizational support and professional values, the mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum observed values were obtained. In finding the correlation between perceived organizational support and professional values, Spearman rho correlation coefficient was used.

Overall, the level of perceived organizational support of the staff nurses is high, as well as their levels of professional values according to the caring, activism and professionalism domains.

Conclusion

According to the results of this study, the perceived organizational support of staff nurses affects their professional values. When nurses perceive high organizational support from their organization, their application of professional values to nursing practice is more likely. The findings indicate that nurses who possess high perceived organizational support protects the dignity, health and safety of their patients and demonstrate professional manners towards the patients. In terms of the domains of professional values, the activism domain had the strongest correlation to perceived organizational support. The staff nurses who work in a tertiary government hospital in Pampanga values advancing their profession and since they serve to a large population – Pampanga and its nearby provinces, it is important to them as part of activism values to eliminate differences in quality of health care services and advocate for their patients.

The results showed that it is important for organizations to provide support to their staff so they will practice their profession in the most ethical way.

Recommendations

Following the presentation of findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are found to be advantageous to:

1. Hospital Administration

- 1.1 A strong management support is encouraged to help nurses maintain a positive perception of the organization, which in turn fosters the application of professional values in nursing practice.

1.2 Enhancement of perceived organizational support and use of professional values through the following policies:

1.2.1 Recognition and rewards policy which can be enhanced by taking into consideration inclusivity and equity among the staff nurses. This provides equal opportunities for recognition regardless of the department or shift of the nurses.

1.2.2 Professional growth and career development policy which may encourage more staff nurses to engage in continuing education.

1.2.3 Open communication and feedback policy to assure that staff nurses can freely voice out their concerns without fear of being judged or punished.

1.2.4 Peer review protocol should be included in the Human Resource Manual to formalize the process and portray that it is consistent and fair. This builds trust among the staff nurses.

2. Staff Nurses

2.1 Actively involve nurses in policy-making and hospital committees to ensure they have participation, and their voices are heard on how to shape their working conditions.

3. Patients

3.1 A study on patient satisfaction on the nursing care quality given to patients to determine the effect of perceived organizational support and professional values of nurses to them.

4. Nursing Administration

4.1 Maintain leadership presence and portray a supportive environment to ensure that nurse leaders are actively participating with the staff in the day-to-

day operations.

4.2 Conduct regular surveys regarding perceived organizational support and professional values of nurses for continuous monitoring and evaluation.

4.3 Strengthen the implementation 360 Degree Feedback Mechanism to maximize its impact and reduce possible fears of retaliation on the part of the staff nurses.

2.2 Maintain or expand employee support programs that includes mental health, fair workload, and flexible scheduling.

5. Future Studies

5.1 A comparative study between government and private hospitals and or different hospital units (clinical versus special care units) to determine if perceived organizational support and professional values of nurses differ by context.

5.2 Studying how higher levels of perceived organizational support among nurses translate to better patient satisfaction.

5.3 Investigating the impact of different nursing leadership styles on perceived organizational support and how they impact professional values.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Informed Consent

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

ACCESSION NO.	PROTOCOL NO. JBLMGH-REC 2024-49B
SPONSOR NO.	N/A
TITLE OF STUDY	Perceived Organizational Support and its Impact on Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Government Hospital in Pampanga
NAME OF PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR/RESEARCHER	Vina L. Salangsang
ADDRESS OF INVESTIGATOR	140 Navalng, Magalang, Pampanga
CONTACT NUMBER	0968 696 1628
NAME OF RESEARCH ASSISTANT	Artie V. Bernabe
CONTACT NUMBER	0968 712 9714

1) Notice of Participation

You are being considered to participate in a research study about Perceived Organizational Support and Its Impact on Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Government Tertiary Hospital in Pampanga . Your ability to participate in the study is described in the procedures below. Before you can take part in this study, it is important that you understand what the study involves. Please read this information carefully and ask any questions that you might have. The research assistant will be available to you in person to explain the purpose of the study, the survey questionnaires and in securing this informed consent. You will be provided a confidential setting while signing this informed consent form. A secured online platform will be used in conducting the survey, where all responses remain confidential. The JBLMGH Research Ethics Committee (REC) has reviewed the purposes of the study and has given a favorable opinion of it.

2) The Purposes of this Study are as follows:

- To determine the level of Perceived Organizational Support of staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga.
- To determine the level of Professional Values of staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga in terms of Activism, Caring and Professionalism.
- To determine if there is a significant relationship between the perceived organizational support and professional values of staff nurses in a government tertiary hospital in Pampanga.

3) Approximate Number of Participants and the Expected Duration of Your Participation in the Study

The study will take place at Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital. About 184 participants will be included in the study. The study will consider all participants who will meet all the eligibility criteria and those who will consent. Informative sessions will be given to the participants to explain the study, its purpose and the survey questionnaires which will last for 10 to 15 minutes only. The participants are given a week to complete the survey which defines the duration of their participation in the study. Participation in this study only involves answering of the two survey questionnaires, no observations, interviews or additional tasks required.

4) Study Treatments and Procedures

This study will determine the relationship between Perceived Organizational Support and Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Government Tertiary Hospital in Pampanga. The study will involve the use of survey questionnaires – Survey of Perceived Organizational Support and Nurses Professional Values Scale – 3. This research will consider all participants who are qualified according to the set criteria and at the same time those who consented to be part of the study. Before conducting the study, the researcher obtained permission from the research setting. The researcher also sought the permission from the developers of the standardized surveys. All participants in the study will be given appropriate information about the research’s purpose and methods. The data that will be gathered will be statistically treated for analysis using Pearson r correlation coefficient or Spearman rho correlation coefficient. An informed consent will be obtained prior to participation in the study. All information gathered will be kept confidential .

5) Benefits

Your participation in this study will help us find out if there is significant relationship between the variables – Perceived Organizational Support and Professional Values among staff nurses in a

government tertiary hospital in Pampanga. The researcher hopes to achieve significant information that will be beneficial to the hospital and nursing administration, staff nurses, and future studies.

Specifically, The benefits include the increased in awareness of the importance of professional values at work, leading to improved decision making, refinement of policies and procedures. This will support the high standards of practice in nursing and involvement in the study will contribute to a wider understanding of perceived organizational support and professional values within their organization, which leads to initiatives on improving their workplace environment.

6) Risks

There is a possibility that you will accidentally share confidential or sensitive information. The researcher and the research assistant would like to guarantee the participants that all acquired information shall be treated confidential.

7) Compensation

No compensation shall be received for the participants.

8) Voluntary Participation / Withdrawal from the Study

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether to take part or not. If you choose not to participate in this study, you are free to refuse and it will not affect your employment in the hospital.

9) Permission for Review of Records, Confidentiality and Access to Records

The researcher/principal investigator through the research assistant will collect information. This information, called data, will be entered without your name, on a report form. In all of these report forms, a code will replace your name. All the data collected will be kept confidential and will be used only as permitted by this consent form.

10) Questions/Information

If you have any questions, you may contact the following:

Principal Investigator – Vina L. Salangasang

Email – salangasangvina@gmail.com. Mobile phone number: 0968 696 1628

Research Assistant – Artie V. Bernabe

Mobile phone number: 0968 712 9714

Chairman, Research Ethics Committee Jose B. Lingad Memorial Regional Hospital

Dr. Sir Emmanuel S. Astudillo

Telephone number: (045) 409-6688

11) Consent Signatures

I FREELY ACCEPT THE INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN THIS STUDY

Printed Name of Participant	
Date (to be entered by participant)	
Signature	

Printed Name of Study Personnel Obtaining Consent	Artie V. Bernabe
Date	
Signature	

Distribution: one copy for the Principal Investigator, one copy to _____
At any given time a study participant may refuse to participate in or request to be withdrawn from the study. The Investigator must respect the request. Wherever possible, the participant will be informed as soon as possible and his/her consent will be requested for the continuation of the study.

APPENDIX B

Permission Requests to the Developers of the Questionnaire

Vina Salangsang <salangsangvina@gmail.com>

NPVS instrument

1 message

Wang, Pengpeng

Tue, Feb 13, 2024 at 1:41 AM

To: "salangsangvina@gmail.com" <salangsangvina@gmail.com>

Cc: "Weis, Darlene"

Dear Vina,

Thank you for your interest in our work on professional values.

Our article, as well as The Nurses Professional Values Scale (NPVS-3) are enclosed. You have our permission to use the NPVS-3 in your proposed research. We are requesting persons who use the NPVS-3 to provide the following at the completion of the research:

An abstract of your research findings using the NPVS-3 which includes a description of the sample.

Our most recent publication regarding the NPVS-3 can be found in the Journal of Nursing Measurement:

Weis, D., & Schank, M.J. (2017). Development and Psychometric Evaluation of the Nurses Professional Values Scale-3. *Journal of Nursing Measurement*, 25(3), 400-410.

Best wishes for success with your research.

Sincerely,

Darlene Weis, PhD, RN

Associate Professor Emeriti

Mary Jane Schank, PhD, RN

Professor Emeriti

APPENDIX C

Questionnaires

10-item Survey of Perceived Organizational Support

Listed below are statements that represent possible opinions that you may have about working at _____. Please indicate the degree of your agreement or disagreement with each statement by filling in the circle on your answer sheet that best represents your point of view about _____. Please choose from the following answers:

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Strongly disagree	Moderately disagree	Slightly disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Slightly agree	Moderately agree	Strongly agree

- (1) The organization values my contribution to its well-being.
- (2) The organization strongly considers my goals and values.
- (3) Help is available from the organization when I have a problem.
- (4) The organization really cares about my well-being.
- (5) My organization wishes to give me the best possible job for which I am qualified.
- (6) The organization cares about my general satisfaction at work.
- (7) The organization takes pride in my accomplishments at work.
- (8) The organization would forgive an honest mistake on my part.
- (9) The organization is willing to extend itself in order to help me perform my job to the best of my ability.
- (10) The organization cares about my opinions.

Nurses Professional Values Scale-Three (NPVS-3)

Indicate the importance of the following value statements relative to nursing practice.
Please fill in the circle next to the degree of importance.

(1 = not important to 5 = most important) for
each statement.

	Not important	Somewhat important	Important	Very Important	Most important
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Engage in on-going self-evaluation.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
2. Respect the inherent dignity, values, and human rights of all individuals.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
3. Protect health and safety of the patient/public.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
4. Assume responsibility for personal well-being.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
5. Participate in peer review.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
6. Establish standards as a guide for practice.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
7. Promote and maintain standards where planned learning activities for students take place.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
8. Initiate actions to improve environments of practice.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
9. Seek additional education to update knowledge and skills to maintain competency.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
10. Advance the profession through active involvement in health-related activities.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
11. Recognize the role of professional nursing associations in shaping health policy.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
12. Establish collaborative partnerships to reduce healthcare disparities.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
13. Assume responsibility for meeting health needs of diverse populations.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
14. Accept responsibility and accountability for own practice.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
15. Protect moral and legal rights of patients.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5
16. Act as a patient advocate.	○ 1	○ 2	○ 3	○ 4	○ 5

Nurses Professional Values Scale-Three (NPVS-3)

	Not important	Somewhat important	Important	Very Important	Most important
	1	2	3	4	5
17. Participate in nursing research and/or implement research findings appropriate to practice.	01	02	03	04	05
18. Provide care without bias or prejudice to patients and populations.	01	02	03	04	05
19. Safeguard patient's right to confidentiality and privacy.	01	02	03	04	05
20. Confront practitioners with questionable or inappropriate practice.	01	02	03	04	05
21. Protect rights of participants in research.	01	02	03	04	05
22. Practice guided by principles of fidelity and respect for person.	01	02	03	04	05
23. Actively promote health of populations.	01	02	03	04	05
24. Participate in professional efforts and collegial interactions to ensure quality care and professional satisfaction.	01	02	03	04	05
25. Promote mutual peer support and collegial interactions to ensure quality care and professional satisfaction.	01	02	03	04	05
26. Take action to influence legislators and other policy makers to improve health care.	01	02	03	04	05
27. Engage in consultation/collaboration to provide optimal care.	01	02	03	04	05
28. Recognize professional boundaries.	01	02	03	04	05

Appendix D

JBLMGH REC Certificate of Approval

small font 11/19/24

 JOSE B. LINGAD MEMORIAL GENERAL HOSPITAL	RESEARCH ETHICS COMMITTEE	
	CERTIFICATE OF APPROVAL	
		REC Form No: 2.6 Version No.: 004 Effectivity Date: April 25, 2024

November 13, 2024

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital REC for implementation:

REC Protocol No.:	JBLMGH-REC 2024-49	Sponsor Protocol No.:	n/a
Principal investigator/s:	Vina L. Salangsang, RN	Sponsor:	none
Title:	"Perceived Organizational Support and Its Impact on Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Government Tertiary Hospital in Pampanga"		
Protocol Version No.:	JBLMGH-REC 2024-49D	Version Date:	November 7, 2024
ICF Version No.:	JBLMGH-REC 2024-49B	Version Date:	September 20, 2024
Other Documents:	Curriculum Vitae		
Member/s of the research team:	Queenie Roxas-Ridulme, RN (Research Adviser)		
Study Site:	JBLMGH		
Type of Review:	Full Board: August 22, 2024	Duration of Approval (From – to):	Frequency of continuing review
	Expedited: September 25, 2024, October 17, 2024 and November 11, 2024	November 11, 2024 to November 11, 2025	Yearly
REC Vice Chair	Name	Signature	Date
	Evelyn B. Manlutac, MD FPOGS		Nov 11, 2024

Investigator Responsibilities after Approval:

1. Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations.
2. Abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research.
3. Submit a letter of withdrawal of the study if he/she decides not to proceed with the implementation of the study.
4. Submit document amendments for REC approval before implementing them.
5. Submit Early Termination Report if appropriate
6. Report any query or complaints
7. Submit negative events, SAE (Serious Adverse Event) or SUSAR (Suspected Unexpected Serious Adverse Reaction) reports to the REC within three (3) days of occurrence.
8. Submit a progress report every 6 months.
9. Report protocol deviation / violation.
10. In case the study is not yet completed, the researcher shall apply for a continuing review 6 weeks before the expiration of the ethical clearance.
11. REC shall conduct site visit, if necessary.
12. Submit Closure/Final Report at the Research Ethics Committee Office after completion of protocol procedures at the study site. Failure to do so, JBLMGH REC will decline future researchers of the same institution.

Received by: Name & Signature: *Vina L. Salangsang* Date: Nov. 25, 2024

Appendix E

Permit to Conduct the Study

6 December 2024

TO: MONSERRAT S. CHICHIOCO, MD, MBA-H, CHA, FPSP, FPCHA
Medical Center Chief II
Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital

THROUGH: EDWIN C. MANIAGO, RN, MSNc
Chief Nurse, Nursing Service Office
Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital

Dear Dr. Chichioco,

Greetings of peace!

I am currently pursuing a Master of Arts in Nursing with a major in Nursing Administration. As part of the requirements for fulfilling the degree, I would like to conduct a study on **Perceived Organizational Support and Its Impact on Professional Values of Staff Nurses in a Government Tertiary Hospital in Pampanga.**

In line with this, may I kindly request your permission and approval to conduct the study in the Nursing Service of Jose B. Lingad Memorial General Hospital (JBLMGH). I have attached the certificate of approval from the JBLMGH Research Ethics Committee to ensure that there will be no psychosocial harm that will be inflicted to the participants in the conduct of the study.

Thank you for considering my request.

Sincerely,

Vina L. Salangsang
Vina L. Salangsang, RN

Dr. Edwin

[Signature]
DEC 10 2024

Noted by:

[Signature]
Asst. Professor. Queenie R. Ridulme, MAN, RN
Research Adviser, FMDS UPOU

3rdFloor, UPOU Main Building, Los Baños, Laguna, Philippines - Telefax: (6349)5366010 or 5366001 to 06 ext 821, 333, 332
fmds@upou.edu.ph - www.upou.edu.ph

Appendix F

Curriculum Vitae

VINA L. SALANGSANG

Home Address: #140 Navaling, Magalang, Pampanga 2011 Philippines

Contact Number: 0968 696 1628

E-mail Address: salangsangvina@gmail.com

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

A. OFW Hospital, San Fernando, Pampanga

May 6, 2024 up to Present : Chief Nurse

January 1, 2024 up to May 5, 2024 : OIC, Chief Nurse

Duties and Responsibilities

- Plans, organizes, and supervises the Nursing Service to provide quality nursing care to patients.
- Collaborates all activities of Nursing Service Department with other services.
- Monitors and evaluates nursing personnel and activities and recommends improvements to ensure that standards are met.
- Formulate and recommends policies for the improvement of patient care.
- Conducts meeting and services programs as venue to discuss issues, updates in new technologies, and other matters for Nursing Service personnel.
- Participates in the preparation of Budget Proposal specifically in Nursing Service.
- Screens applicants for the nursing service.
- Prepares and submits nursing service reports as required.
- Approves procurement plan to ensure complete hospital supplies and equipment.
- Coordinates with the Medical Center Chief in developing programs, policies, budget and other plans for these needs of the nursing service and the improvement of patient care.

December 05, 2022 up to December 31, 2023: OIC, Assistant Chief Nurse

Duties and Responsibilities

- Directs the performance of nursing managers, head nurses and staff relative to the established standards of nursing practice within the period of assignment.

Helps interpret and direct a sound plan of organization and effective system of communication retrieve to the established policies and objectives of nursing services division.

- Recommends workforce planning and distribution patterns necessary to provide quality patient care.
- Creates and maintains a professional environment that values nurses and other members of the health care team, treats patients with dignity and respects diversity.
- Adheres to established norms of conduct based on the Philippine Nursing Law and other legal, regulatory and institutional requirements relevant to safe nursing practice.

August 1, 2022 to December 04, 2022: Nurse Manager, 5th and 6th Floor

Duties and Responsibilities

- Participates in the assessment activities to determine the individual needs of the patients and program needs of the staff.
- Applies ethical reasoning and decision-making process to address situations of ethical distress and moral dilemma.
- Supports nursing education and preceptorship providing an optimal learning environment.

OFW Hospital is the country's first hospital dedicated to Overseas Filipino Workers (OFWs) and their dependents. It is designed to be a seven-story, 100-bed secondary level government hospital. At the moment, it is operating as a Level 1 hospital, treating and serving different illnesses.

B. Career Break

April 8, 2021 up to July 31, 2022

- Focused on finishing requirements for my research subject.
- Provided care for my mother who had undergone major operation until she made full recovery.

C. St. John Paul II Medical Center Corporation, Magalang, Pampanga

August 16, 2019 up to April 7, 2021: Head Nurse, General Nursing Unit

St. John Paul II Medical Center Corporation (SJPMCC) is the first private hospital in Magalang, Pampanga. It has an approved 41-bed capacity. It is licensed by the Department of Health as Level I hospital and accredited by the Philippine Health Insurance Corporation. The hospital offers services from its various units like the

Emergency Room, General Nursing Unit, OR/DR, Outpatient Department, Laboratory, Pharmacy, and Radiology Department.

Job Summary

Manages the General Nursing Unit and is directly responsible for its administration, supervision, and overall operations.

- Conducts routine daily patient rounds to monitor the actual patient care delivered and plan for any improvement as needed towards reaching the goal of the unit.
- Plans, develops, implements, and evaluates the standards of care and health care practices as needed according to the standards of nursing practices/hospital policy.
- Possesses a working knowledge of each patient's diagnosis, history, goal of treatment, and

appropriate nursing care.

- Demonstrates respect and regard for the dignity of all patients, families, visitors and fellow employees to ensure a professional, responsible, and a courteous environment.
- Recommends ways to reduce expenditures and enhance revenues without compromising quality of services.
- Collaborates with HR on the recruitment and selection of qualified employment candidates, following all policies, guidelines, and applicable laws.

D. AC Sacred Heart Medical Center, Angeles City

June 06, 2018 up to July 25, 2019: Staff Nurse, Neonatal Intensive Care Unit/Nursery

Company Profile

The AC Sacred Heart Medical Center, located at McArthur Highway, Sto. Domingo Angeles City is a five-story, 135-bed private hospital. It has the following departments – Medicine, Pediatrics, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Surgery, Anesthesiology, Pathology and Laboratory Medicine, Radiologic Imaging, Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation and Cancer Institute.

Job Summary

Provide care to newborn infants and families when the newborn's health condition requires more support than traditional postnatal wards. Work with well babies and newborns with a variety of problems such as congenital defects, prematurity, surgical problems, and other body malformations.

Duties and Responsibilities:

Nursery

- Receives the baby right after delivery and provide immediate care.
- Identifies infant name bracelet or ID wrist band and foot printing.
- Check for any congenital anomalies and abnormalities.
- Do thermoregulation using droplight to avoid hypothermia.
- Assess weight and anthropometric measurements of the baby.
- Monitor vital signs for the first 4 hours of life.
- Suction secretions, nasal and oral as needed.
- Refer properly and endorse to the attending physician about the delivery.
- Administer oxygen if necessary or as per doctors order.
- Observe closely for signs of respiratory distress during the first 24 hours of life especially for preterm and post term babies.

NICU

- Maintain parenteral infusion.
- Recognize numerical deviation in blood gas measurement.
- Apply monitoring equipment.
- Administer oxygen appropriately on the basis of hypoxia.
- Passing of orogastric tube, suctioning and maintaining tube when necessary.
- Report promptly all significant variation in patient's condition to the physician in charge.
- Recognize respiratory failure and the need for ventilator support.
- Helps in the transport of high risk infant.

E. Family Leave

June 2016 up to June 2018

- I got married and eventually I was involved in volunteer works in the community while taking care of my son.

F. Prince Sultan Cardiac Center, Riyadh Saudi Arabia

October 16, 2015 up to May 16, 2016 : Staff Nurse, Pediatric Post-op Surgical Ward

Company Profile

The Prince Sultan Cardiac Centre (PSCC) is in Riyadh the capital of Saudi Arabia. These 174 beds, advanced teaching hospital provides a major portion of the cardiac services for the Kingdom. PSCC offers a full range of diagnostic and management facilities for patients ranging in age from neonate to elderly. There are four clinical departments: Adult Cardiology, Paediatric Cardiology, Cardiac Surgery, and Cardiac Anaesthesia.

Job Summary

Responsible for ensuring pediatric patients' recovery after surgery by monitoring vital signs, looking for signs of complications and administering medications until discharged.

Duties and Responsibilities

- Obtain initial cardiovascular and respiratory assessment of post-operative patients upon admission.
- Provide nursing care to patients following surgical procedures: BT Shunt, PDA ligation, Fontan procedure, Glenn procedure, pre and post cardiac catheterization.
- Possess knowledge and skills in ECG interpretation and temporary pacing.
- Knowledge of equipment: cardiac monitor, defibrillator, pulse oximeter, infusion pump, syringe pump, syringe driver, doppler, dinamap, ECG machine.
- Assist physicians in examining and providing care for the patient throughout the post operative period.

G. Security Forces Hospital Programme, Riyadh Saudi Arabia

June 20, 2012 to June 20, 2015: Staff Nurse, Out-patient Department

Company Profile

Security Forces Hospital Program (SFHP) is one of the leading tertiary health care providers in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Security Forces Hospital with its advanced and integrated facilities and systems; medical, clinical, and ancillary systems, including primary care clinics, specialty care clinics, and 500 beds inpatient facility combined with an integrated surgical facility and supported by highly trained medical and other staff with various specialty are the key ingredient to the delivery of high-quality patient care to the patients of SFHP.

SFHP has achieved CCHSA (Canadian Council on Health Service Accreditation) award in 2003 and was reaccredited in 2006.

Job Summary

To achieve the set mission and vision of the institution by monitoring the quality care provided and promote best nursing care practice within its scope of practice. Rotated in various subspecialties of the Out-patient Department (e.g., Internal Medicine, Cardiology, ENT, Pediatrics, OB-Gyne, etc).

Duties and Responsibilities

- Maintains high standards of patient care on the unit on a 24-hour basis.
- Interacts effectively with patients, family, and team members to

maintain standards of professional care to patients, families, and visitors.

- Maintains own professional growth.
- Assists with controlling and directing the unit to encourage quality patient care and staff satisfaction.

Special Assignments:

- Magnet Accreditation
Program Member, Unit
Based Council (OPD)
December 2014 to June
2015

Magnet Accreditation
Program Secretary, Quality
and Safety Council December
2014 to June 2015

H. Mother Teresa of Calcutta Medical Center, Pampanga Philippines

March 08, 2010 to April 26, 2012: Staff Nurse, Pediatrics Intensive Care Unit (PICU)

Company Profile

Mother Teresa of Calcutta Medical Center is a 142-bed medical center complex made up of three buildings joined together to come up with a very spacious, efficacious and well-ventilated hospital environment that will serve our clientele. Established in 2006, the hospital consists of state-of-the-art facilities – Emergency Room Complex, Medical – Surgical Intensive Care Unit, Labor and Delivery Rooms, Nursery, Neonatal ICU, Pediatric ICU, Out-born ICU, Clinical Laboratory (Tertiary Level), 12 Operating Room Theaters, Heart Station, Pulmonary Unit, Radiologic Imaging Department, Pharmacy and Medical Arts Building.

Job Summary

Responsible for managing the care of the infant or child experiencing life-threatening problems requiring complex assessment, high intensity therapies and interventions, and continuous nursing vigilance.

Duties and Responsibilities

- Continuously monitors patient's vital signs, neuro vital signs, input and output and other pertinent patients on hourly basis or as necessary and provides appropriate nursing intervention.
- Possess skills in operating equipment such as ventilators, defibrillators, infusion pumps, glucose test meter and patient's monitor and interprets significantly.

- Collaborates with other members of the healthcare team with regards to the patient's plan of care.
- Keeps an updated record of all emergency drugs.
- Provides appropriate nursing procedures which includes: suctioning, tracheostomy care and the like.
- Feeds patient through NGT or OGT etc.
- Assist physician in preparing patient for examination, testing and or procedures; scheduling and/or explaining procedures/tests to patient and family.
- Follows guidelines/protocols established by the nursing department.
- Administers medications by appropriate route with consideration for patient safely; utilizes specialized training to prepare and administer immunizations/medications.
- Perform laboratory procedures when necessary.
- Responsible for facilitating efficient patient flow within the unit.
- Identifies specialized patients needs and informs attending physicians and appropriate member of the staff.
- Assist with data collection regarding patient-related issues including maintaining database/referral network of health services.
- Performs other related duties as assigned in the absence of the Head Nurse when necessary.
- Be involved in the setting and maintenance of high clinical standards on the unit by attending continuous professional trainings, seminars and lecture.
- Demonstrate and promote non-discriminatory practice.
- Charging patients appropriately using the hospital's computer system.
- To perform other duties requested by Nursing Department.

I. Leewel's Vibro Plant, Pampanga Philippines

June 10, 2009 to February 26, 2010: Company Nurse

ELIGIBILITY RECORDS

- Nurse Licensure Examination June 2009

TRAININGS/SEMINARS/WEBINARS ATTENDED

2024 **Our Nurses. Our Future. Harnessing the Economic Power of Care**
University of Santo Tomas Hospital

2023 **Burn Bright Not Out, Keeping Staff Engaged**
OFW Hospital

Leadership Training

2022

Basic ECG Training and Seminar

OFW Hospital

Basic Life Support and Advanced Cardiac Life Support Course

Philippine Heart Association Philippine College of Cardiology

Deciphering the Writings On the Wall

Virtual Webinar Part IV Philippine Hospital Association

IV Leadership Summit

3M Health Care Academy Lecture 3M Company

Psychosocial Care for Adult Cancer Patients

Oncology Nursing Webinar Series Health Futures Foundation, Inc.

Optimizing Oxygenation in a Critically Ill Child: Recognizing and Managing the Challenge on Refractory Hypoxemia and Old Gadget, New Trick: The Reemergence of High Flow Nasal Cannula

PICU MRT Season 2 Webinar Series

DELEX Pharma International, Inc./Pediatric ICU Forum

Dose-Dosenang Sinugod sa Emergency Room: Anong gagawin ninyo ngayong may COVID-19 Pandemic?

Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

Giyera sa Panahon ng Pandemya: Apektado ba tayo?

Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

COVID-19 Medications: Epektibo Ba? Stop COVID Deaths Webinar

Series University of the Philippines

OMICRON: What We Should Know & What We Should Do

Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

2021 Ethico-Moral and Ethico-Legal Issues Among Nurses in the COVID-19 Pandemic

Philippine Nurses Association, Inc.

FACT OR FAKE: Be COVID-19 Social Media Smart!

Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

COVID-19 Outbreak sa Probinsiya Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series

University of the Philippines

Breakthrough Infections: Bakunado na Ako, Bakit COVID (+) Ako Ngayon?

Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

Laging Handa: World Class Filipino COVID-19 Innovations
Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

READY BA TAYO? A Conversation on the COVID-19 Delta Variant
Stop COVID Deaths Webinar Series University of the Philippines

The Delta Variant: What Every Frontliner Needs to Know
Stop COVID Deaths: Virtual International Conference (Part 3) Webinar
Series University of the Philippines

- 2020**
- PPE Doffing and Donning Training**
St. John Paul II Medical Center Corporation, Magalang Pampanga
 - COVID-19 Rapid Test Training**
St. John Paul II Medical Center Corporation, Magalang Pampanga
 - Waste Management Training**
St. John Paul II Medical Center Corporation, Magalang Pampanga

EDUCATION:

Master of Arts in Nursing, Major in Nursing Administration
University of the Philippines - Open University (UPOU) Los Baños, Laguna,
Philippines

Bachelor of Science in Nursing Angeles University Foundation Angeles City,
Philippines March 2009

Bachelor of Science in Psychology Angeles University Foundation Angeles City,
Philippines
April 2006

PERSONAL DATA

Date of Birth:	November 27, 1984
Place of Birth:	Pampanga, Philippines
Civil Status:	Married
Age:	40 years old
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Religion:	Iglesia ni Cristo
Height:	5'2"
Weight:	118 lbs.